

The Uncertainty Principles and Time Considerations

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 12, 2019

In quantum mechanics, there exist two important uncertainty relations, one involving momentum and position and the other time and energy. For the momentum-position relation, one often calculates a variance of position and momentum and denotes these as measuring uncertainty. There is a math identity relating the product of the variances of a function and its Fourier transform. For a wavefunction, the Fourier transform is the momentum wavefunction and so this identity is applied. For the case of energy and time, things seem to be more nebulous. The uncertainty principles in quantum mechanics are advertised as restricting the precision of information. For example, one can only know position and momentum up to certain error terms, while in classical mechanics, a particle is treated as a point at a position x at time t with energy E and no uncertainty.

The purpose of this note is attempt to examine issues of uncertainty in quantum mechanics. It is known that for a particle following classical mechanics, one can develop a density picture in which a particle has a density of $1/v(x)$. In such a case, one can calculate a variance for both position and momentum and there is no longer a concept of the particle being at position at an exact time. If one is not following the particle on its trajectory, then there is uncertainty in the system as to the position and momentum of the particle at any given time, but this is not based on any fundamental measurement restriction. It seems rather to be based on limited experimental information. Given the correspondence principle, the density $W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction should approach $1/v(x)$ for high energy eigenvalues. In such a case, one can calculate position and momentum variances for $W(x)$ and argue that there is an inherent restriction in the system, but this is strange as the system is already approaching the classical limit. It is also strange that one needs to construct a wave packet in order to see classical like motion, when the classical system can be described as a density system with density $1/v(x)$.

In a quantum mechanical system, one can calculate an average kinetic energy at each point x (not kinetic energy density) which equals that of classical mechanics, regardless of the energy eigenvalue (small or big). This average, however, seems to be taken over a cycle time $1/\text{energy}$ and for small energy eigenvalues this time is large relative to time scales in the system. Thus, the average, although allowing for energy conservation, does not necessarily seem to describe motion from position x_1 at t_1 to x_2 at t_2 . In other words, the average is taken over a long period of time. We consider in this note, issues of time, including the cycle time, and try to see if these time scales can shed light on uncertainty.

Classical Mechanical Density

In classical mechanics, one often uses Newton's second law to describe the motion of a particle through space. At each point x at time t one knows the velocity and energy and so the system is deterministic. It is possible, however, to consider the system in terms of density $1/v(x)$ and so lose all information about time (1). In such a case, one takes a one dimensional line and

breaks it into equal tiny Δx segments. A potential is present, so the velocity $v(x)$ is different in each. One sets density equal to Δt in each segment or $\Delta x / v(x)$. In such a case, there is no fundamental uncertainty restriction in the classical system, there is only a lack of measurement information. One is unable to follow the particle in time and so creates an average picture. It should be noted that technically at each point x with density $dx/v(x)$, one can have velocity in the forward or negative direction. The density does not distinguish between the two, but these two scenarios are separated in time by a large amount. Thus, the average density $dx/v(x)$ may take at least as long as the time to complete a cycle (say in an oscillator) to be established. Thus, the spatial density in this classical problem is not really an instantaneous quantity. (One might argue that one could establish the density from consideration of the particle moving in one direction, but it seems that technically one should have both forward and backward motion included in a full average used to create the density $dx/v(x)$).

In this classical mechanical system, one removes time, and describes a long time average as representing the system. Such an average, however, only partially describes the system. One can calculate both a position and momentum variance in such a case. These describe uncertainty due to the statistical approach used, and not due to inherent restriction on measurement in the system.

Position variance = $\int x^2 \frac{1}{v(x)} dx - x_{ave}^2$ where x is integrated over the bounds of the system. In some cases, $x_{ave}=0$.

$1/v(x) = 1/\sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$ where $V(x)$ is the potential. Here one is using the positive value of $v(x)$ everywhere. Otherwise the variance and in fact the density would vanish on average (at least for an oscillator) as the positive velocity contributions would cancel those of the negative.

To calculate the momentum variance one needs a momentum density. One can start with dt and write dp/F where F =force. Then the variance is given by:

$\int p^2/F dp - p_{ave}^2$

For an oscillator $F=-kx$ and one again only considers positive values of x . One can express x in terms of p using $x = \sqrt{2/k (E-p^2/2m)}$.

In both cases, one obtains nonzero variance suggesting uncertainty, namely that in the statistical model used. With more experimental measurements, one would not have to use such a statistical model in the first place, and there would be none of this uncertainty.

According to the correspondence principle, for high quantum energy eigenvalues, the quantum density (at least at certain points) should approach the classical density $dx/v(x)$. For the quantum oscillator, one sees various humps which approximate $1/v(x)$ roughly at maxima of the humps. One could calculate a momentum variance and also a position one for each. In quantum mechanics, the uncertainties are supposed to be restrictions on the ultimate measurement precision. In the high energy eigenvalue case, however, classical mechanics is

being approached and there is no such precision restriction it seems. Again, this seems to be an issue of lack of measurement information in the particular statistical picture used, rather than any physical restriction. It seems that one could calculate a variance for the various humps in the density $W(x)W(x)$. This would give local position variances at different points in space (the peaks of the humps) and would perhaps give more information about local uncertainty without needing to construct a wave packet.

Issues of Time and the Wavefunction

Let us consider as an example, a particle bouncing in a one dimensional well of length L . Then the eigensolutions are $\sin(2n\pi x/L)$ where $k=2n\pi/L$. Interestingly, as the energy eigenvalue becomes very large, the length L does not change. Often, classical physics is said to describe large length scales and quantum mechanics, small ones, but that does not seem to be the case at least in this example. According to the correspondence principle, large n should approach the classical picture. Is it possible to obtain any information without forming a wavepacket?

Consider that the frequency of the sine wave is becoming very large and its wavelength very small. The sine function is actually created by the interference of a forward and a backward moving wave, meaning this quantum average (in a classical sense) is created over a long period of time (the time required for the classical particle to move forward and then return to the initial point). One, however, treats $\sin(kx)$ as a average that exists at an instant in time which is perhaps misleading.

For the case of a tiny wavelength and large momentum, one may ask whether one can obtain any information regarding uncertainty (without a wavepacket). It seems that the width of a hump of the sine wave should represent uncertainty in position. The uncertainty in momentum could be approximated as $2p$ as the momentum might be p in the forward or backward direction. If one uses $\Delta x \Delta p = \hbar/2$ then $\Delta x = (\hbar/2) / (2p) = \hbar/4p$ which shows that Δx is becoming very small in this hand-wavy approach. It is in fact, on the order of the size of a hump of the sine wave. (Note: Some people use $\Delta x \Delta p = \hbar$.) Thus, one has an uncertainty in p , but it consists entirely in not knowing whether p is in the forward direction or backward and has nothing to do with a measurement restriction on p . Δx being small means that the particle is defined in a small region $\hbar/4p$ so the wavefunction picture (without a wavepacket) seems to describe classical behaviour. Using $\int \psi^* \hat{H} \psi dx = \int \psi^* (-\hbar^2/2m) \nabla^2 \psi dx$ to calculate the average kinetic energy also gives the classical value of $p^2/2m$.

The next question is to ask what happens when one considers a system with a potential $V(x)$ where $V(x)$ is not constant. In such a case, there is a well defined average kinetic energy. In fact, given that quantum mechanics uses $V(x)$, the classical potential, it seems that the entire theory is based on energy conservation. For example, consider that a quantum particle, such as an electron, has complicated internal behaviour such as zitterbewegung which gives it an "average velocity" v and a spread in space, i.e. the particle does not exist at a point. When placed in a potential, it will scatter into various new momentum states, which also have a spread in x . These states in turn will scatter until one has a resonance described by $\exp(iE_n t)$ where E_n is the energy eigenvalue. The time $1/E_n$ represents the cycling time needed to cycle through the

states. These states make up the quantum resonance it seems, but also must create an average kinetic energy to allow for constant energy as one is using $V(x)$ in the equation. This average kinetic energy, however, need not exist at an instant in time, rather it is an average taken over a long period of time it seems. For an oscillator, the mechanical period is related to $\sqrt{k/m}$ (k =the spring constant), while $E_{\text{ground state}} = \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega$ where $\omega = 2\pi/\text{mechanical period}$. Thus, the average occurs over a time of the same order that it takes the oscillator to complete an entire cycle. One can, however, write an expression for the classical kinetic energy at each x by:

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right) W(x)/W(x) + V(x) = E$$

The first term is the average classical kinetic energy $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$, but one does not think in terms of a particle existing at x at t and having $v(x)$, rather this seems to be a mathematical average.

It seems, however, that in a hand-wavy manner, one may consider the following:

$\Delta x = v(x)/E_n$ which is the distance a classical particle with $v(x)$ would travel in the cycle time $1/E_n$.

If Δx is very small (which it is not for the ground state of a quantum oscillator), then one might approach a classical picture. In such a case, $1/E_n$ for large E_n becomes very small meaning, perhaps, that one can consider an instant in time with an average $v(x)$. Thus, the cycle time, $1/E_n$ might be important for calculating Δx values instead of the traditional variance of x using the wavefunction approach.

It should be noted that there is another average velocity in the quantum picture, namely $\hbar \frac{d}{dx} W(x)/W(x)$. This is related to a change in density namely:

$$\frac{d}{dx} [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x) \frac{dW(x)}{dx}$$

Thus, it seems that there is a flux velocity $\hbar \frac{d}{dx} W(x)/W(x)$ which differs from $v(x)$ the classical velocity. The flux velocity allows for the formation of physical density and also of average kinetic energy of plane waves which ultimately leads to $v(x)$. It should be noted, however that both of these velocities seem to be mathematically created averages that do not a priori need to correspond to any real motion from x_1 t_1 to x_2 t_2 . It seems, however, that in the case of large energy eigenvalues, $v(x)$ approaches a physical motion from x_1 t_1 to x_2 t_2 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that it does not seem necessary to create wavepackets to mimic classical motion, as classical motion can be described in terms of spatial density. This statistical picture of classical mechanics, however, "loses" some information and leads to variances in x and momentum which are not physical restrictions (but consequences of information loss). We

argue that a similar thing may be happening in quantum mechanics as high energy eigenvalue solutions should lead to a density which approaches the classical $1/v(x)$. We suggest that averages in this statistical picture of classical mechanics and in quantum mechanics are taken over a long period of time (relative to motion in the system). For quantum mechanics, this time is equal to the cycle time $1/E_n$. In quantum mechanics, one can mathematically calculate the average momentum of a set of plane waves with different weights and have them yield the classical kinetic energy with $v(x)$ at each x , but this $v(x)$ does not necessarily have any physical reality as a velocity from x_1 to x_2 . We suggest, however, that $v(x)/E_n$ may define a Δx which can be used as an uncertainty in position. If this is small in terms of the length scale, i.e. the cycle time is very small, quantum mechanics may be approaching classical mechanics.

References

1. Majernick V and Opatiny Y. Entropic uncertainty in classical quantum Oscillator (J Phys A Math Gen, 1995, UK) <http://www.ktf.upol.cz/tom/clanky/jpa96-ent.pdf>
2. Reeder, Mark 2012 <https://www2.bc.edu/mark-reeder/FourierEvecs.pdf>
3. J S Briggs 2008 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 99 012002
4. P. Signell 2000 Michigan State U.
<http://www.physics.iitm.ac.in/~sunilks/F=ma%20from%20QM.pdf>
5. Dhar, Deepak. The Bohr Correspondence Principle Tata Institute of Technology
<https://www.ias.ac.in/article/fulltext/reso/021/06/0565-0573>